

Research assessment by ANECA drives green open access in Spain

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Abstract: Since the beginning of the century, there has been a notable growth in green open access, driven by initiatives and transformations in the publishing system. In Spain, although legislation already mandated self-archiving, effective implementation did not occur until 2023, when the National Agency for Quality Assessment and Accreditation (ANECA) adopted the principles of DORA and CoARA, making repository deposit mandatory for participation in evaluation processes (sexenios and accreditations). This led to a sharp increase in deposits, especially during open calls, clearly visible in institutional repositories, such as that of the University of Granada. This change demonstrates that a well-designed evaluation policy can accelerate the adoption of green open access, although it also highlights that obligation has been more influential than ethical conviction.

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49 Dear Scientometric Editors,
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51 Since the start of the century, open access has steadily grown, both in the number of available
52 works and in the number of institutional repositories¹. While green open access initially showed
53 significant growth, it was later surpassed by other routes such as gold open access (Gargouri et al.,
54 2012; Piwowar et al., 2018), a shift already foreseen by Harnad (2010). Currently, it is estimated
55 that over 40% of the world's scientific literature is available via open access, with green access
56 being particularly prevalent in fields such as biomedicine and the physical sciences (Robinson-
57 Garcia et al., 2020). This progress has been driven by many factors, including foundational
58 manifestos (Berlin and Budapest), institutional (Wenaas & Gulbrandsen, 2022) and supranational
59 policies (cOAlition S). It also owes much to the development and improvement of digital
60 infrastructures (Björk et al., 2014), transformative publishing agreements (Gadd & Troll Covey,
61 2019), more permissive editorial practices (Borrego et al., 2021), and events like the COVID-19
62 pandemic (Torres-Salinas, 2020). Although it still faces challenges, its evolution reflects sustained
63 commitment from both the scientific community and policymakers.
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65 In Spain, since the enactment of Law 14/2011, of June 1, on Science, Technology, and Innovation,
66 researchers have been required to deposit a copy of the final accepted version of their publications
67 and associated data in open access institutional or thematic repositories. This law was replaced by
68 Law 17/2022, of September 5, which removed embargo periods for self-archiving. According to
69 studies, all Spanish public universities have official repositories that support green open access,
70 which has contributed to around 50% of publications and 49% of Web of Science-indexed
71 publications from universities being openly available (De-Filippo et al., 2023), a figure that did
72 not reflect the legal requirements. This situation changed when, in 2023, the National Agency for
73 Quality Assessment and Accreditation (ANECA) joined DORA and CoARA².
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75 That same year, the call for Research Activity Bonuses (*sexenios*), which evaluates scientific
76 merits every six years based on five key contributions, stopped focusing solely on bibliometric
77 metrics and, for the first time, introduced a requirement for publications to be open access. Initially
78 flexible, this requirement became mandatory in 2024, and publications not deposited in
79 repositories were no longer considered for evaluation. This change also extends beyond the
80 *sexenios* system, directly affecting the accreditation processes for Associate Professor (*Profesor*
81 *Titular*) and Full Professor (*Catedrático*), as their publication evaluation criteria are directly
82 inherited from the latest *sexenios* call. Although the legislation had already mandated this action,
83 it had never been operationally enforced. Starting in 2023, many researchers were, for the first
84 time, compelled to interact with institutional repositories, since the gold route (more familiar to
85 them) did not exempt them from depositing in repositories. The introduction of a mandatory self-
86 archiving requirement into the *sexenios* system has had immediate and measurable effects. The
87 clearest indicator is that 14,787 applications were submitted in the latest call³, meaning that, in a
88 hypothetical scenario with no overlap between applications, up to 73,935 works should be
89 available in open access.
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¹ <https://roar.eprints.org/view/year/>

² <https://www.aneca.es/-/aneca-se-adhiere-a-la-san-francisco-declaration-on-research-assessment-dora-y-a-la-coalition-for-advancing-research-assessment-coara->

³ <https://www.aneca.es/documents/20123/292418/estadisticas-pleno-16-06-maq2.pdf/5b439fd1-ed7e-d10f-0b40-ebcb5f3b57b1?t=1750083198386>

91 This effect is clearly measurable by examining data from institutional repositories where
 92 publication deposits can be used as a proxy for self-archiving activity, though not as a direct
 93 measure of green open access, as they also include outputs published via other routes (e.g., gold
 94 or hybrid). To observe the impact of this policy, we obtained data from DIGIBUG⁴, the repository
 95 of the University of Granada. **Figure 1** shows how, during the 2024 and 2025 *sexenios* call periods,
 96 the University of Granada experienced a sharp increase in deposits. At this institution, one of those
 97 with the highest number of applications submitted nationwide, the institutional repository data
 98 show two unprecedented peaks in activity, coinciding exactly with the opening of the calls. In the
 99 2024 and 2025 calls, 504⁵⁶ and 911⁷⁸ applications were submitted, respectively, while 2,895 and
 100 3,909 works were deposited during the corresponding periods. In just the months of January and
 101 February 2024 and 2025 alone, 16% of all deposits from the last decade were concentrated,
 102 representing 59% of the accumulated submissions in those same two-month periods across the
 103 same timeframe.

105 **Figure 1. Monthly publication submissions to the institutional repository of the University of**
 106 **Granada, 2016–2025.** Months with open *sexenios* calls are shaded in gray.

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⁴ <https://digibug.ugr.es/>

⁵ <https://www.aneca.es/-/sexenios-de-investigación-concedidos-a-funcionarias/os-desagregados-por-institución-universidades-y-opi->

⁶ <https://www.aneca.es/web/guest/-/concedidos-el-95-13-de-los-sexenios-de-investigación-de-profesorado-laboral>

⁷ <https://www.aneca.es/documents/20123/292418/estadisticas-pleno-16-06-maq2.pdf/5b439fd1-ed7e-d10f-0b40-ebcb5f3b57b1?t=1750083198386>

⁸ https://www.aneca.es/documents/20123/297509/estadisticas_Pleno_18_07_maq3.pdf/86a456d0-a0a7-3161-4f25-432efd7db16c?t=1752841513736

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This behavior observed at the University of Granada is clearly generalizable to other R&D centers and universities, and it reveals that, despite the data, the green open access route was far from widespread prior to 2024. Furthermore, in the Spanish case, it once again becomes clear that the “carrot” model, offering visible incentives to researchers (Jiménez-Contreras et al., 2003), is what is effectively promoting self-archiving. Evaluation policies, when aligned with personal benefits and clear institutional requirements, can be powerful tools to foster the green open access route. However, this also reveals a darker reality, self-archiving is not being adopted primarily out of ethical conviction but because it has become a *sine qua non* condition for obtaining recognition. In other words, obligation outweighs willingness, which runs counter to the CoARA philosophy, which envisions a change rooted in conviction rather than imposition. In any case, the Spanish model offers a clear example of how to give a decisive push to repository depositing and self-archiving practices, creating favourable conditions for the expansion of green open access.

Declarations

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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